

Questionnaire for participants in the DTA project

 Mandatory questions are marked with an asterisk (*)

Thank you for participating in the DTA project and for doing the speaking tasks. Now we kindly ask you to answer the questionnaire. In this questionnaire we ask for your personal data. We also ask you about the speaking tasks and about your Finnish language learning.

You can use a translator, and you can write your answers in your mother tongue or in a language other than Finnish in the open questions.

1. Moodle-ID *

Your Moodle username. Do not write your name or any other personal information!

2. Gender *

- Woman
- Man
- Other
- Prefer not to answer

3. Age *

- 18-28
- 29-39
- 40-50
- 51-61
- 62 or older

4. What is your mother tongue/first language? You can mention multiple. *

5. What other languages can you speak and use in everyday situations? Select other languages than your mother tongue/first language. *

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Dari
- English
- Spanish
- Farsi, Persian
- Italian
- Chinese
- Kurdish
- Nepalese
- Portuguese
- Polish
- French
- Romanian
- Swedish
- German
- Somali
- Finnish
- Tagalog, Filipino
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Hungarian
- Urdu

- Russian
- Vietnamese
- Estonian
- Other, please specify _____

6. What language are you using in this questionnaire? *

7. When have you moved to Finland? *

- 2025
- 2024
- 2023
- 2022
- 2021
- 2020
- 2019
- 2018
- 2017
- 2016
- 2015
- Before 2015

8. For how long have you learned Finnish? *

- 0-3 months
- 3-6 months
- 6-9 months
- 9-12 months

- 1-1,5 years
- 1,5-2 years
- 2-2,5 years
- 2,5-3 years
- 3-5 years
- 5-7 years
- more than 7 years
- more than 10 years

Opinions on the speaking tasks

9. How did the speaking tasks seem? *

	1 Difficult	2 Quite difficult	3 Not difficult nor easy	4 Quite easy	5 Easy
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

10. What did you think of the speaking tasks? *

	1 Completely disagree	2 Quite disagree	3 I can't say	4 Quite agree	5 Completely agree
a) It was easy for me to understand the instructions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b) The speaking tasks were interesting.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
c) I learned something new (for example vocabulary).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
d) The speaking tasks were similar to the tasks in the Finnish course.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e) The test was of suitable length for me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
f) The speaking tasks were of an appropriate level for me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

11. Would you like to practice speaking independently with similar speaking tasks? If you answered yes, please briefly describe what you would like to practise. *

Yes.

No.

12. You can write comments or more information on questions 10-12.

Questions about learning Finnish

13. How do you learn Finnish? You can write examples, for example on a course, self-study online, talking with a Finnish neighbour.

14. Do you use a translator (for example Google Translate, DeepL) when learning a language? If you answered yes, please briefly describe how and in which situations.

Yes.

No.

15. Do you use artificial intelligence (AI: for example ChatGPT, CoPilot) when learning a language? If you answered yes, please briefly describe how and in which situations.

Yes.

No.

16. What do you think about the following statements regarding written and spoken Finnish language?

	1 Completely disagree	2 Quite disagree	3 I can't say	4 Completely agree	5 Completely agree
a) I know there is spoken (puhekieli) and written (kirjakieli) Finnish.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b) I have learned both spoken and written Finnish (on the course or otherwise).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
c) I can easily understand written Finnish (kirjakieli).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
d) I can easily understand spoken Finnish (puhekieli).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e) When I write and speak, I use only written Finnish (kirjakieli).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
f) When I speak and write, I use only spoken Finnish (puhekieli).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

17. Do you have any other comments or questions for the DTA project.
